

Effectiveness of Realia Utilization to the Cursive Handwriting Skills of Grade Two Learners

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effect size of the utilization of realia to the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners. The study utilized a quasi-experimental design. A total of 60 Grade Two learners in the Labon Elementary School in Sulop District, Division of Davao del Sur were identified through purposive sampling. A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized in the gathering of data. Mean, Sample T-test, and Eta-squared were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed on the pretest mean score of the control group and experimental group; both had average mean scores in cursive handwriting skills before being exposed to the realia approach. In addition, on the posttest mean score it was revealed that the experimental group, which was exposed to the realia, demonstrated a significantly higher posttest mean score categorized as Very High, compared to the control group, which had a mean score categorized as Average. Moreover, on the significant difference between the mean gains scores of students in the control group and the experimental group revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between the two groups' posttest scores. Lastly, on the effect size of utilization of realia to enhance the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners results revealed a large effect size. This large effect size emphasizes the significant and impactful role that utilization of realia play in enhancing cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners. Thus, the study recommends teachers should experiment with various realia materials, adapting them to suit their students' needs, and evaluate the effectiveness of these tools in their classrooms.

KEY WORDS

1. Realia 2. cursive handwriting skills 3. quasi-experimental design

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1. Introduction

Cursive writing, a style of penmanship where letters are joined together in a flowing manner, is often valued for its aesthetic appeal and efficiency in writing. This form of handwriting emphasizes fluid, continuous strokes, which can enhance the speed of writing compared to print. It also helps in developing fine motor skills and hand-eye coordination. Despite its

decline in use in the digital age, cursive writing remains an important skill in certain educational contexts and is sometimes seen as a way to preserve traditional writing techniques.

In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Labon Elementary School, Sulop District, the problem is majority of the Grade Two learners do not master the cursive handwriting

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

skills based on the Quarterly Assessment conducted using the Programme for International Student Assessment or PISA-LIKE TEST in Filipino 2 of the school year 2023-2024. Several things must be done to help learners in cursive handwriting properly and correctly. The alignment, letter formation, line quality, slant of letters, sizing, and spacing, and give emphasis on the shape and distance of the letters. The researcher, being a Grade Two teacher, ventures on this study hoping to resolve this existing academic problem and contribute to the enhancement of teaching strategies for young learners. Hence, the study aimed to provide information on the effectiveness of Realia in enhancing the Cursive Handwriting Skills of Grade Two Learners in Labon Elementary School, Sulop District, Davao Del Sur Division. The specific objectives of the study are the following: a.) to determine the pretest mean score of the control group and the experimental group. b.) to determine the posttest mean score of the control group and the experimental group. c.) to determine if there is a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the learners in the control group and the experimental group, and d.) to determine the effect size of the utilization of realia to the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners. At .05 level of significance, the following hypothesis was tested: a.) There is no significant difference between the mean gain scores of the learners in the control group and the experimen-

tal group, and b.) There is no significant effect of utilization of realia to the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners

The study benefited several individuals. School administrators can utilize the findings to inform decisions regarding curriculum creation and resource distribution, underscoring the significance of handwriting programs. Moreover, teachers can establish dynamic classrooms that enhance cursive writing proficiency while accommodating varied learning requirements through interactive activities. For students, cursive writing provides cognitive advantages, including greater memory, language processing, creativity, and self-expression. Subsequently, future researchers may expand upon this work to investigate effective methodologies for handwriting instruction and the influence of realia on educational achievements.

Presented in Figure 1 is the conceptual framework showing the variables of the study. This presented the interaction between the independent variable and dependent variable. The figure displays that utilization of realia is the independent variable of the study. On the other hand, the dependent variable of the study is the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners. Ultimately, the aim of this study was to determine the effect size of the utilization of realia in enhancing the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners.

2. Methodology

The following section outlined the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It included the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically a non-equivalent pretest-posttest control group design, which is distinguished by the lack of random assignment and is considered effective in clinical and educational research (White Sabarwal, 2014). The design included two intact groups: a control group receiving traditional instruction and an experimental group receiving the intervention. The control group served to establish a baseline for evaluating the impact of the independent variable (the intervention) on the dependent variable (Palys Atchison, 2021). Both groups underwent pretest and posttest procedures for a descriptive analysis of their performance, in line with Shadish et al.'s (2002) recommendations for quasi-experimental designs when random assignment is not possible. The quantitative analysis aimed to assess whether significant differences existed in the pretest and posttest scores between the groups, providing insights into the effectiveness of the intervention on student performance.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study was conducted at Labon Elementary School in Sulop District, Division of Davao del Sur, using a purposive sampling strategy to select respondents based on the researcher's awareness

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—This study followed a systematic approach to data gathering. First, permission was obtained from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges and the Division Superintendent. Subsequently, a parental consent form was created to inform guardians about the study's details, risks, benefits, and voluntary participation. The questionnaire, thereafter, underwent content validation by experts, which led to revisions

of the necessary information for this technique (Campbell et al., 2020). The sample comprised two intact grade 2 sections, with thirty pupils in the experimental group and thirty in the control group. The experimental group received the intervention, where realia was used to improve cursive handwriting, while the control group received traditional instruction limited to lectures. Both groups underwent a pretest, and the researcher, who oversaw both groups, conducted regular meetings lasting 50 minutes, in line with the class schedule, during the second and third quarters. This targeted selection and the structure of the study ensured a focused examination of the effects of the intervention on the students' cursive handwriting skills.

2.3. Research Instrument—The researcher developed a questionnaire to assess the pretest and posttest performance of both the control and experimental groups when exposed to the use of realia. The questionnaire was validated by experts to ensure its reliability and validity. Both groups took a pretest and a posttest using a 20-item assessment designed to measure the cursive handwriting skills of the respondents. The test results were subjected to item analysis, with any rejected items removed from the final version of the assessment.

for clarity and relevance. Additionally, a pilot test with 30 learners was conducted to assess the instrument's reliability and clarity. Once the necessary adjustments were made, the finalized questionnaires were then administered in person to build trust and gather thoughtful responses. Finally, the completed surveys were securely stored for analysis, which was meticulously conducted using SPSS to ensure data reliability and validity.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean, Independent Samples t- test, and Eta Squared were the statistical tools employed in the study.

3. Results and Discussion

This section highlighted the results and discussions of the study. The presentation started with the discussion on the mean scores of pretests and posttest for the control group and experimental group. Followed by, the discussion on the significant difference of the mean gain scores of the two groups. Lastly, to determine the effect size of the utilization of realia on the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners.

3.1. *Pretest Mean Score of the Control Group and Experimental Group*—Table 1 presented the pretest mean score of the control group and experimental group. Based on the result, the pretest mean scores of both the control and experimental groups were interpreted as Average, this also means that the cursive handwriting skills of the learners showed moderate improvement. The control group achieved a mean score of 9.89, while the experimental group recorded a slightly higher mean score of 10.73. These results indicate that, prior to the intervention, both groups exhibited similar cursive handwriting skills, with no significant disparity between their performance levels. This establishes a baseline for comparing the effectiveness of utilizing realia in enhancing the cursive handwriting skills of Grade Two learners.

Table 1. **Pretest Mean Score of the Control Group and Experimental Group**

Group	N	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Control Group	30	9.89	Average
Experimental Group	30	10.73	Average

Legend: 1.00 – 4.00: Very Low, 4.01 – 8.00: Low, 8.01 – 12.00: Average, 12.01 – 16.00: High, 16.01 – 20.00: Very High

3.2. *Posttest Mean Score of the Control Group and Experimental Group*—Table 2 flaunted the results on the posttest mean score of the control group and experimental group. The results highlighted a notable difference in the cursive handwriting skills of the control and experimental groups after the intervention. The control group achieved a mean score of 11.83, which remained within the Average range, indicating that the scores of the learners were satisfactory, indicating minimal improvement. In contrast, the experimental group, which was exposed to realia, attained a significantly higher mean score of 16.47, interpreted as Very High, which means that the mean score of the experimental group was exceptional, demonstrating outstanding performance on the learner’s cursive handwriting skills. This substantial increase suggests that the use of realia as an instructional tool was effective in enhancing the cursive handwriting skills of Grade Two learners.

3.3. *Significant Difference between the mean gain scores of the students in the control group and experimental group*—Table 3 revealed the analysis of the significant difference

Table 2. **Posttest Mean Score of the Control Group and Experimental Group**

Group	N	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Control Group	30	11.83	Average
Experimental Group	30	16.47	Very High

Legend: 1.00 – 4.00: Very Low, 4.01 – 8.00: Low, 8.01 – 12.00: Average, 12.01 – 16.00: High, 16.01 – 20.00: Very High between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups. The result shows a clear distinction in their posttest performance. With a t-value of 8.021 and a p-value of .000, the results indicate a statistically significant difference between the two groups. This implies that the intervention, specifically the use of realia, had a substantial positive effect on the cursive handwriting skills of the experimental group compared to the control group, which did not receive the same intervention”

Table 3. **Significant Difference Between the Mean Gain Scores of the Students in the Control Group and Experimental Group**

Variable Paired	N	df	t-value	p-value	Descriptive Interpretation
Posttest of Control Group and Experimental Group	60	58	8.021	.000	Significant

3.4. *Effect Size of the Utilization of Realia to the Cursive Handwriting Skills of the Grade Two Learners*—Table 4 provided insight into the effect size of Utilization of Realia to the Cursive Handwriting Skills of the Grade Two Learners. The effect size calculation for the utilization of realia to enhance the cursive handwriting skills of Grade Two learners yielded an eta-squared value of 0.525, which is interpreted as a Large effect. This indicates that the intervention had a substantial impact on improving the cursive handwriting skills of the experimental group. The t-value of 8.021 further supports the significant difference observed between the control and experimental groups.

Table 4. **Effect Size of the Utilization of Realia to the Cursive Handwriting Skills of the Grade Two Learners**

N	t-value	Eta-Squared	Descriptive Interpretation
60	8.021	0.525	Large

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to test the effectiveness of Realia in enhancing the Cursive Handwriting Skills of Grade Two Learners. The specific objectives of the study are the following: a.) to determine

the pretest mean score of the control group and the experimental group. b.) to determine the posttest mean score of the control group and the experimental group. c.) to determine if there is a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the learners in the control group and the experimental group, and d.) to determine the effect size of the utilization of realia to the cursive handwriting skills of the grade two learners. The following were the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—The pretest mean scores for both the control and experimental groups were classified as Average, indicating that the learners' cursive handwriting skills exhibited considerable improvement. The control group attained a mean score slightly lower than to that of the experimental group. The results demonstrate that, before the intervention, both groups displayed comparable cursive handwriting abilities, with no significant differences in their performance levels. This creates a benchmark for evaluating the efficacy of employing realia in improving the cursive handwriting abilities of Grade Two students.

These findings align with Perea et al. (2016) explain that cursive handwriting supports fine motor development and cognitive engagement through the complex hand movements required for continuous strokes. This aligns with the observed moderate cursive handwriting skills in the study, as the baseline performance reflects a need for further refinement through targeted intervention.

For the post-test mean score, the results highlighted a notable difference in the cursive handwriting skills of the control and experimental groups after the intervention. The control group achieved a mean score that remained within the Average range, indicating that the scores of the learners were satisfactory, with minimal improvement. In contrast, the experimental group, which was exposed to realia, attained a significantly higher mean score interpreted as Very High, meaning their performance was exceptional and demonstrated outstanding improvement in cursive handwriting skills. This substantial increase suggests that the use of realia as an instructional tool was effective in en-

hancing the cursive handwriting skills of Grade Two learners.

This aligns with Micallef and Newton (2022) highlighted how realia makes lessons engaging and relevant by providing concrete examples that bridge abstract concepts with everyday experiences. This finding supports the improved handwriting performance of the experimental group, as realia likely engaged students more effectively than traditional methods, making the learning process enjoyable and meaningful.

For the analysis of the significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups, the result shows a clear distinction in their posttest performance. The results indicate a statistically significant difference between the two groups. This implies that the intervention, specifically the use of realia, had a substantial positive effect on the cursive handwriting skills of the experimental group compared to the control group, which did not receive the same intervention.

This corroborated with Gambari et al. (2014), that the use of realia in education, defined as real-life objects incorporated into teaching, has been widely recognized for enhancing student engagement and learning. Realia connects abstract concepts to real-world experiences, making lessons more tangible and interactive. The practical application of real-life objects helps students relate theoretical content to their everyday lives, improving understanding and retention.

Meanwhile, the effect size calculation for the utilization of realia to enhance the cursive handwriting skills of Grade Two learners was interpreted as a Large effect. This indicates that the intervention had a substantial impact on im-

proving the cursive handwriting skills of the experimental group. The statistical analysis further supports the significant difference observed between the control and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—This result was supported by Berninger et al. (2020) that in handwriting instruction, realia can offer hands-on experiences that help students develop fine motor skills essential for writing. By engaging in tactile activities like tracing letters on sandpaper or shaping letters with clay, students can improve motor coordination, which directly impacts their handwriting proficiency. These tactile experiences not only reinforce letter formation but also support writing fluency by making practice sessions more interactive and meaningful.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that

the Department of Education integrate realia into the curriculum from Kindergarten to Grade 3 and include it in teacher training and instructional materials to enhance cursive handwriting skills. School heads should promote its classroom use to foster more engaging learning environments, while teachers are encouraged to incorporate realia into their daily lessons and pursue professional development to use it effectively. Students should actively engage with realia during handwriting instruction to improve their skills and motor development. Lastly, future researchers are urged to investigate the long-term and broader impacts of realia on handwriting and literacy across various educational settings.

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